

Perception and sensory acceptance of salty taste by individuals who work/study on different shifts

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Abstract

Night activity, whether at work or in teaching, has been increasing significantly in recent years. However, the human being has a daytime nature and sleep restriction that can influence the modulation of various situations managed by the circadian cycle, such as eating behaviour. Thus, we evaluated the perception and sensory acceptance of salty taste by individuals who work/study in different shifts. Three groups of individuals were recruited: Control group (individuals that study during the day and do not work at night), Group 1 (individuals that study in the evening) and Group 2 (individuals that work overnight). The individuals were submitted to a detection threshold test using sodium chloride solutions and to a sensory acceptance test using a structured hedonic scale and a Just-About-Right scale for salty taste in meatball. Sleep time decreased significantly from the Control group to Group 1, and then even more to Group 2. The detection threshold of Group 2 was significantly higher than the other groups. Nevertheless, few statistical differences were found between the three groups in terms of sensory acceptance of salty taste. Concluding, the change in the sleep pattern, either due to a shift change or in the amount of sleep time, influences the salty taste sensory perception.

Keywords: circadian cycle, nightshift workers, night-school students, detection threshold test, sensory acceptance

Introduction

Night activity, both work and study, has been increasing significantly in recent years and, although there has been an increase in night activity, human beings are diurnal by nature and their sleep-wake pattern is determined by the light/dark cycle. This phenomenon, called the circadian cycle [1], is regulated by a central clock in the brain and corresponds to a physiological cycle with periodicity of approximately 24 hours. In 2017, researchers won the Noble Prize in Medicine for discovering the molecular mechanisms that control the circadian rhythm [2] and demonstrating that the internal clock of plants, animals and human beings is responsible for readapting the physiology with high precision to the different phases of the day, regulating critical functions, such as behaviour, hormone levels, sleep, body temperature and metabolism. Consequently, circadian desynchrony is involved in several pathological conditions. Nevertheless, no studies in the literature that have evaluated the relationship between changes in sleeping patterns and sensibility to basic tastes and the sensory acceptance of food were found. Thus, we aimed to evaluate the perception and sensory acceptance of salty taste by individuals that work/study on different shifts.

Experimental

Three groups of individuals were recruited: Control group (individuals that study during the day and do not work at night); Group 1 (individuals that study in the evening); and Group 2 (individuals that reverse the shifts, i.e., that work overnight). Each group was composed by thirty-seven individuals, who were characterised regarding the usual bedtime and sleep time. Moreover, the individuals were only included in each group if they had been in the same 'routine' for at least one year to guarantee their adjustment to those sleeping/waking and working/studying patterns [3].

The individuals were submitted to a detection threshold test (in two repetitions) using sodium chloride solutions (Table 1). Samples of sodium chloride were presented in pairs (distilled water and solution), from the most diluted concentration to the more concentrated. The panellist should indicate whether there was any difference between the two samples (distilled water and solution). In the case of a negative answer (no difference detected), the next plastic cup with solution along with one of distilled water were offered. The pairs of plastic cups were offered until the panellist detected a difference between the samples in two successive concentrations of sodium chloride. When this occurred, the analysis was stopped, and the mean of these two successive concentrations was taken as the detection threshold for that panellist [4]. The panellists were also submitted to a sensory acceptance test using a structured hedonic scale and a Just-About-Right scale (both of nine points) for salty taste in meatballs with different sodium chloride concentrations (Table 1).

Table 1: Sodium chloride concentrations for the detection threshold test and acceptance of salty taste of meatballs.

Detection threshold (g sodium chloride/L*)	Acceptance test (g sodium chloride/kg meat)
2.00	32.60
1.40	22.80
0.98	15.84
0.69	11.08
0.48	7.60
0.34	5.32
0.24	4.08
0.16	2.88
R = 0.7	R = 0.7

*ISO 3972:2011 [5]

R = geometric proportion (ISO 3972:2011).

The means of usual bedtimes were compared using the Student's t test for independent variables, while the analysis of variance followed by the Tukey test were performed for sleep time and detection threshold. Moreover, the general linear model having sample and group as factors, as well as the interaction between such factors, was applied to the sensory acceptance data, and the means were compared through the Tukey test. These analyses were performed using the Minitab 17 (Minitab Inc.) software and the 0.05 significance level. Moreover, the linear regression analysis between the results from the Just-About-Right scale as a function of sodium chloride concentrations was performed using the Excel 2013 program.

Results and discussion

When asked about their usual bedtime (Table 2), individuals of the Control group and Group 1 had a clear pattern in their answers, i.e., the individuals slept at different times, but always at the same time every night. However, individuals of Group 2 did not have any pattern to their answers, once people who work overnight often work a shift scheme called 12/36 h, in which they work for 12 h overnight and rest for 36 h before the next shift. When they work the night shift, they sleep during the day, and this may begin at 4 h or 8 h or even as late as 15 h. However, when they do not work and have a day's rest, they sleep during the night. Regarding the sleep time, there was a decrease significantly from the Control group to Group 1 and then even more for Group 2 (Table 2).

Table 2: Characterization of individuals (mean \pm SD; n = 37).

Group	Usual bedtime	Sleep time (min)
Control	23h18min \pm 48min ^a	431.4 \pm 50.7 ^c
1	00h12min \pm 56min ^b	376.2 \pm 77.0 ^b
2	-	319.5 \pm 91.7 ^a

Different letters for usual bedtime indicate significantly different means by Student's t test ($p \leq 0.05$).Different letters for sleep time indicate significantly different means by Tukey test ($p \leq 0.05$).

The detection thresholds between the Control group and Group 1 did not differ significantly for the salty taste. However, both were significantly lower than Group 2 (Table 3). This shows that a change in the sleep pattern, whether it be in the change of shifts or in the number of hours slept, influences the salty taste sensory perception. The individuals that work overnight are less sensitive to the salty taste than individuals that study in the evening or do not have changes in their sleep pattern.

Table 3: Detection threshold (average \pm SD; n = 37) for sodium chloride by different groups.

Group	Sodium chloride concentration (g/L)
Control	0.34 \pm 0.16 ^a
1	0.42 \pm 0.28 ^a
2	0.63 \pm 1.88 ^b

Different letters indicate significantly different means by the Tukey test ($p \leq 0.05$).

The sensory acceptance of the salty taste of meatballs was affected only by sample and group. Regarding samples, as the sodium chloride concentration increased, the degree of liking and the ideal of intensity also

increased up to certain concentrations (Figure 1). At the last concentration of sodium (32.60 g sodium chloride/kg meat, sample 8), there was a significant decline in the degree of liking (Figure 1A; statistic result not shown). However, from the concentration of 22.80 g sodium chloride/kg meat (sample 7), there was a significant change in the ideal of intensity of salty taste (statistic result not shown) because it stops being 'ideal intensity', when the average reaches a value close to 5, reaching 'more intense than ideal' (means higher than 6) (Figure 1B). Such results indicate that the increase in the sodium chloride concentration from certain concentrations had become prejudicial to the sensory acceptance.

Comparing the degree of liking between the different groups, the Control group showed a significantly higher degree of liking for samples regarding the salty taste in comparison to the others (Figure 1A; statistic result not shown), while the ideal of intensity was significantly higher than Group 1 (Figure 1B; statistic result not shown), although the three means are near to 5, which represents the 'ideal intensity' of salty taste. These last results are corroborated by the linear regression analysis (Figure 2), which shows concentrations of sodium chloride close to each other for an ideal intensity of salty taste ($y = 5$): 14.65 g sodium chloride/kg meat, 16.68 g sodium chloride/kg meat and 14.93 g sodium chloride/kg meat for the Control group, Group 1 and Group 2, respectively.

Figure 1: Salty taste acceptance through hedonic (A) and JAR (B) scales of the beef meatballs by sample (averages from $n = 111$) and group (averages from $n = 296$). Legend for samples: 1) 2.88, 2) 4.08, 3) 5.32, 4) 7.60, 5) 11.08, 6) 15.84, 7) 22.80, and 8) 32.60 (values in g sodium chloride/kg meat). Legend for groups: Control group: individuals who study during the day and do not work at night, Group 1: individuals who study in the evening, and Group 2: individuals who reverse the shift (work overnight).

Figure 2: Ideal of intensity of salty taste in function of the sodium chloride concentration in the meatballs. Legend: Control group: individuals who study during the day and do not work at night, Group 1: individuals who study in the evening, and Group 2: individuals who reverse the shift (work overnight).

The average daily salt consumption varies among different populations. Salt can be found in a lot of daily intake food and it is difficult to calculate the total daily consumption because the preference and evaluation of salt consumption in such studies is usually self-referred. Thus, methods for measuring salt intake may not be reliable. On the other hand, the detection threshold test can reflect indirectly on the daily salt consumption because an increased salt taste sensitivity threshold score was associated with salted food intake and salty taste preference [6].

In this way, individuals from Group 2 could need more salt to detect the salty taste, contributing to their higher salt consumption. However, considering the different tests for characterizing the taste function in humans, the detection threshold test for salty taste is not as efficient as a suprathreshold test (stimuli concentrations between the recognition threshold and the terminal threshold) for reflecting the liking of individual for such taste [7, 8]. Thus, other analyses should be performed in the future, providing new complementary results, for example, an investigation of the total daily consumption of salt through individual food intake survey methods.

Conclusion

The detection threshold of Group 2 was higher than the other groups, indicating that a change in the sleep pattern, either due to a shift change or in the amount of sleep time, influences the salty taste sensory perception. Nevertheless, changes in sleep pattern did not have important influences on the salty taste acceptance. Deeper studies need to be performed to better understand relationships between circadian cycle and sensory perception and acceptance of foods.

References

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